

Morphometric Measurements of the Internal Acoustic Meatus in the Human Skull

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ABSTRACT

The internal auditory canal (IAC) is another name for the internal acoustic meatus (IAM). The labyrinth blood vessels and the two significant cranial nerves—the facial and vestibulocochlear nerves (7th and 8th)—pass via this canal (internal acoustic meatus.) This canal has proven clinically significant since it is the location of auditory neuromas. The internal auditory canal (IAC) requires both quantitative and morphometric measurement in order to determine its anatomical structure and the structure that passes through it.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES: The present study was planned to study the morphometric parameters of internal acoustic meatus by using Image-J application. Following parameter was measured in this study: -Anterior wall length of IMA bilaterally, Posterior wall length of IMA bilaterally and Medial wall length of IMA bilaterally.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: The present descriptive cross-sectional study was carried at Department Anatomy, Index Medical Hospital and Research Centre, Indore (MP), India, from November 2021 to March 2024. Study Material: Clean and dry temporal bone was used for the study. Study Design: Descriptive cross-sectional study. Sample Size: A total 100 Temporal bone, (50 right, 50 left).

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS: The data was represented in Mean±SD. The data was further compared using Unpaired t-test.

RESULT

The length of the anterior wall on both the sides (right and left) was compared the right anterior wall was 11.91 ± 1.20 and the left anterior wall was 11.63 ± 1.74 and the difference was statistically non-significant. (p-value, 0.36). The range of the right side was 10.01-14.71 and the left side was 8.65-16.81. The length of the posterior wall in both the sides (right and left) was compared the right posterior wall was 8.52 ± 1.57 and left posterior wall was 8.69 ± 1.47 and the difference was statistically non-significant.

CONCLUSION

The data obtained from the study was further compared with the past studies and it showed varied difference in morphometry of IAM, this may be due to racial and genetic diversity within the study population. The findings of this study will give crucial information of IAM morphometry, age related changes and gender differences.

INTRODUCTION

The internal auditory canal (IAC) or IAM internal acoustic meatus is an important short bony canal that lies between the posterior surface of the petrous pyramid and the bony labyrinth within the dense petrous bone of skull; the IAC opens medially to the posterior canal fossa through the porus acoustics. Several essential nerves pass through this canal. The seventh and eighth cranial nerves pass through the IAC, and this canal has been clinically important as a region in which acoustic neuromas occur. (1)

The entire canal has a length of about 1 cm and extends laterally inside the bone. The Lateral end of the IAM is formed by the thin cribriform plate of bone. This plate separates the cochlea and vestibule from the IAM, and is defined as a fundus of the internal acoustic meatus (FIAM). The FIAM constitutes also the medial wall of the labyrinth. The height and width of the FIAM range from 2.5 to 4.0 mm and from 2.0 to 3.0 mm, respectively.

The FIAM transmits from the cranial cavity to ear the following structures: facial nerve, intermediate nerve, labyrinthine artery and vestibulocochlear nerve which divides near the lateral end of IAM into two parts: a cochlear nerve and vestibular nerve(2)

Many investigators have studied the IAC on radiographs, on casts, in dissected temporal bones, and in histologic sections and have found that the dimensions, shape, and volume of the normal adult IAC vary widely, even between two sides of the same individual, as well as among different individuals. (3,4,5-7)

The Otologists and radiologists are well aware of the variations in normal canal dimensions and have developed diagnostic criteria for canal size. Recently it has been proposed that a narrowed IAC may be responsible for sensorineural hearing loss and vertigo. Knowledge of the normal dimensions of the internal acoustic canal is more important for determination of the clinical anomalies and tumor processes. Quantitative and morphometric measurements of length of different walls such as anterior, posterior and medial wall is important for better surgical intervention and management of conditions occurs due to the anomalies of IAM and its structure passing through the canal. (8, 9) Thus, the present study was aimed to study the morphometric measurements (anterior, posterior and medial wall) of IAM.

Materials and Methods: The present descriptive cross-sectional study was carried at Department Anatomy, Index Medical Hospital and Research Centre, Indore (MP), India, from November 2021 to March 2024 The dried temporal bones of human skulls were randomly selected and the age, sex and race of the temporal bone were not known.

The study was approved by Institutional Ethics Committee.

Study Material: Clean and dry temporal bone was used for the study.

Study Design: Descriptive cross-sectional study.

Sample Size: A total 100 Temporal bone, (50 right, 50 left).

Sample size was estimated using software power analysis and sample size, version 8 (PASS-2008).

Inclusion Criteria:

- Left and right both side dry temporal bone without any break.
- Clean, dry temporal bone was included in the study.
- **Exclusion Criteria:** Bone with any
- sign of fracture and deformities was excluded from the study.

Study Tools: Following instruments was used in the study-

Injecting Gun for Filling of the silicone in internal acoustic meatus

Fixator silicone gel: A caulking machine has a cartridge or tube which contains silicone that can be triggered and deposited into areas where there is a gap or space. A silicone gel sheet is a soft, flexible, self-adhesive dressing. They are of two types-

Condensation Silicone: Supplied as a two paste / putty system. It has a good detail reproduction

Addition silicon: It has high dimensional stability, excellent flow properties and good detail reproduction. It is expensive and has short shelf life.

Procedure Methodology: The impression of the internal acoustic meatus was taken by injecting the silicone material into the internal acoustic meatus. After injecting the material its leave 16-20 hours to harden inside the internal acoustic meatus and then taken out from internal acoustic meatus. All the samples were photo graphed with high resolution camera with same distances. Above mentioned parameters of the IAM were calculated and measured with the help of

Image J Software: Image J is fast, reliable and most widely used image processing software as it is free open-source program, making it low cost and dependable tool for researchers. Application is developed by National Institute of Health Sciences (GOI). ImageJ is a Java-based image processing program developed at the National Institutes of Health and the Laboratory for Optical and Computational Instrumentation (LOCI, University of Wisconsin).

Statistical analysis: The data was represented in Mean±SD. The data was further compared using Unpaired t-test. Paired t-test was used to compare within the same parameters. Further, pearson correlation was done between the two variables.

RESULTS

Table – 1 Comparison between the right and left side of (Anterior, Posterior and Medial) part of IAM

Table – 2 Paired Sample t-test for the length of wall of IAM.

Paired t-test Statistics				
Parameters	Range	Mean±SD	P-value	
Anterior wall of length			0.3686	
Right	10.01-14.71	11.91±1.20		
Left	8.65-16.81	11.63±1.74		
Posterior wall of length			0.5775	
Right	6.01-12.24	8.52±1.57		
Left	6.02-11.73	8.69±1.47		
Medial part of length			0.8947	
Right	5.74-8.41	6.76±0.68		
Left	4.61-8.19	6.50±0.82		
Anterior wall length (Right-Left)		Mean±SD 2.28±1.87	Std Error 0.265	P-value 0.292
Posterior wall length (Right-Left)		1.173±1.90	0.269	0.523
Medial part of length (Right-Left)		0.260±0.98	0.139	0.067

Figure – 1 Bar Graph represents the Right and left side length of anterior wall of IAM.

Figure – 2 Bar Graph represents the Right and left side length of posterior wall of IAM

Figure – 3 Bar Graph represents the Right and left side length of medial part of IAM

Table – 3 Pearson correlations between the parameters of Right side of IAM.

Parameters	AW	PW	MW
AW	1	.728**	.451**
PW-	1	.112	
MW -	-	1	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01level (2-tailed)

Wall Of Internal Acoustic Meatus. AW – Anterior wall, PW – Posterior wall, MW – Medial wall.

Table – 4 Pearson correlation between the parameters of Left side of IAM.

Parameters	AW	PW	MW
AW	1	.683**	.476**
PW	-	-	.206
MW	-	-	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01level (2-tailed)

Wall Of Internal Acoustic Meatus. AW – Anterior wall, PW – Posterior wall, MW – Medial wall.

- The data is represented in tables and figures.
- The data includes mean and SD of right and left side of anterior, posterior, medial, lateral, superior, posterior wall of IAM.
- The unpaired and paired t-test was calculated to compare the mean of both side of IAM
- Further, Pearson correlation was carried out between the variables of right and left side respectively. (Table -3,4)
- The length of the anterior wall on both the sides (right and left) was compared the right anterior wall was 11.91 ± 1.20 and the left anterior wall was 11.63 ± 1.74 and the difference was statistically non-significant. (p-value, 0.36). The range of the right side was 10.01-14.71 and the left side was 8.65-16.81. Further paired statistics showed that right and left anterior wall had 0.283 ± 1.87 and it was statistically non-significant. (p-value, 0.29). (Table- 1,2; figure -1)
- The length of the posterior wall in both the sides (right and left) was compared the right posterior wall was 8.52 ± 1.57 and left posterior wall was 8.69 ± 1.47 and the difference was statistically non-significant. (p-value, 0.57). The range of the right side was 6.01-12.24 and the left side was 6.02-11.73. Further paired statistics showed that right and left posterior wall had 0.173 ± 1.90 and it was statistically non-significant. (p-value, 0.523). (Table- 1,2; figure- 2)
- The length of the medial part of IAM in both the sides (right and left) was compared the right medial part was 6.76 ± 0.68 and left medial part was 6.50 ± 0.82 and the difference was statistically non-significant. (p-value, 0.89). The range of the right side was 5.74-8.41 and the left side was 4.61-8.19. Further paired statistics showed that right and left medial part had 0.260 ± 0.98 and it was statistically non-significant. (p-value, 0.067). (Table- 1,2, figure- 3)

DISCUSSION

The internal acoustic meatus (IAM) is one of the most important canals that provides a connection or passage between the posterior cranial fossa and the internal ear of the skull. The IAM canal opens onto the posterior surface of the temporal bone, and this canal is called the internal acoustic pore (PAI) . (10,11) Quantitative and morphometric measurement of the internal auditory canal (IAC) is important to understand the essential to establish the anatomical structure and the structure passing through it that help surgeons for microsurgery of the cerebellopontine angle and

acoustic neuroma, which may produce bone changes and is an important intracranial pathology. With the advancement of microsurgical and radiological techniques, the surgery of acoustic neuromas is shifting from the hands of the neurosurgeon in the posterior cranial fossa, to the otologist in the internal auditory canal. (12, 13) Thus, the present study was aimed to study the morphometric parameters (anterior, posterior, medial) of Internal acoustic meatus with the help of Image J Software.

The distance from the greatest curvature of the blunt anterior margin of the porus to the most lateral point of the fundus in the lamina cribrosa (LC) area for the cochlear nerve is termed as the

Length of the anterior wall: In the present study when the length of the anterior wall on both the sides (right and left) was compared the right anterior wall was 11.91 ± 1.20 mm and the left anterior wall was 11.63 ± 1.74 mm and the difference was statistically non-significant. (p-value, 0.36). The range of the right side was 10.01-14.71 mm and the left side was 8.65-16.81 mm. Further paired statistics showed that right and left anterior wall had 0.283 ± 1.87 mm and it was statistically non-significant. (p-value, 0.29).

The study was in accordance with another study conducted by (Day et al, 1994) estimated the length of the anterior wall was 14.5 mm on right side (14). According to the study conducted by Akin Saygin D in 2022, the anterior wall measured 13.64 ± 2.6 mm on the left and 12.06 ± 2.81 mm on the right. (16) In their 1995 work, Sakashita & Sando detailed the anthropometry of IAM. They measured the anterior length of IAM and discovered (11.3 ± 2.6 mm) and ranges from (5.0 mm and 15.8 mm) (1) (Kolagi et al. ,2010) found the length of anterior length to be 12.94 ± 2.34 mm on the right side and 13.09 ± 2.38 mm on the left side. (17) all above findings were in continuous with our present finding. Further, the distance from the posterior lip of the porus to the most lateral point of the fundus in the lamina cribrosa (LC) area.

Length of the posterior wall: In the present study when the length of the posterior wall in both the sides (right and left) was compared the right posterior wall was 8.52 ± 1.57 mm and left posterior wall was 8.69 ± 1.47 mm and the difference was statistically non-significant. (p-value, 0.57). The range of the right side was 6.01-12.24 mm and the left side was 6.02-11.73mm. Further paired statistics showed that right and left posterior wall had 0.173 ± 1.90 and it was statistically non-significant. (p-value, 0.523).

The mean length of anterior wall of internal acoustic meatus was high as compare to posterior wall.

Several other researchers studied the length of posterior wall of IAM, and found different variations in length of posterior wall of IAM. A study by (Ebenius et al, 1934) reported the average mean 3.0-16.0 mm which was less than our own study. (18) (Sato & Takida, 1962) found 5.0-10.2mm, (Valvassori & Piece, 1964) reported 4.0-11.0 mm, (Papangelou, 1972) found 6.0 – 14.0 mm. (19, 20, 6). In their 1995 work, Sakashita & Sando detailed the anthropometry of IAM. They measured the posterior length of IAM and discovered (8.3 ± 2.1 mm) and ranges from (3.5-11.8mm) (1) All the above findings of different researcher is same as our present study. A study by (Mamatha Y et al, 2018) reported that the average length of the posterior surface was (range 5- 8mm). (21)

Lastly, the **Length of the medial part of the IAM** was determined and it may be defined as the distance from the posterior lip of the porus to the medial margin of the foramen singular.

In our present study when the length of the medial part of IAM in both the sides (right and left) was compared the right medial part was 6.76 ± 0.68 mm and left medial part was 6.50 ± 0.82 and the difference was statistically non-significant. (p-value, 0.89). The range of the right side was 5.74-8.41mm and the left side was 4.61-8.19mm . Further paired statistics showed that right and left medial part had 0.260 ± 0.98 mm and it was statistically non-significant. (p-value, 0.067).

According to a study by Mamatha Y et al. (2018), the length in left side was 4.13 ± 0.73 mm and 3.86 ± 0.7 mm on the right side. (21) One of the studies that included the anthropometry of IAM in addition to its three-dimensional structure was reported by Sakashita & Sando in their 1995 article, they concluded the length of medial wall was between 2.2 mm and 7.9 mm (5.1 ± 1.7)mm .(1) Another study by Kolagi et al, 2010 reported that the length of medial wall in right is 6.5 ± 1.15 mm and left is 6.44 ± 1.43 mm. They discovered that the centre section of IAM measured 4.8 mm (3.2-6.5 mm) in height and 4.9 mm (3.1-7 mm) in width. (17) In a different study, Farahani R.M. et al. (2012) measured the length of medial section of the IAM, finding that it was 5.04 ± 1.04 mm. (2). A study by Akin Saygin 2022 et al, reported the length of right medial wall 6.83 ± 1.59 mm and left medial wall 6.31 ± 1.47 mm in 83 dry skull studied (16), these study was accordance to our present study. Moreover, at last we also carried out the pearson correlation between the variables of IAM in both Right and Left side, and we found significant correlation between different variables. Thus, after studied all the length of wall we can conclude that there are variations in the dimensions by different studies with respect to our own study. The variations of dimensions may be attributed to the differences in race of the study population.

CONCLUSION

The present study was carried out to obtain the measurements of different parameters of IAM among temporal bone of adult dry skulls. The data obtained from the study was further compared with the past studies and it showed varied difference in morphometry of IAM, this may be due to racial and genetic diversity within the study population. The findings of this study will give crucial information of IAM morphometry, age related changes and gender differences. It will provide greater help to the otolaryngology surgeon during presurgical evaluation for having a successful surgery and minimize the related problems.

REFERENCE

- [1]. Sakashita, T. & Sando, I. Postnatal development of internal auditor canal studied by computer aided threedimensional reconstruction and measurements. *Ann. Otol. Rhinol. Laryngol.*, 104(6):469-75, 1995
- [2]. Farahani, Rr. M. Nooranipour, & Nikakhtar, K. V. Anthropometry of internal acoustic meatus. *Int. J. Morphol.* 2007;25(4):861-865.
- [3]. CampJO, CillyEIL. Thesignificanceofasymmetryof the poriacusticias an aid in diagnosisof eighth nerve tumors. *Am I RoentgenoI*1939;41:713-8.
- [4]. ValvassoriGE, Pierce RH. The normal internal auditory canal. *Am J Roentgenol* 964;92:123241
- [5]. Amjad AH, Scheer AA, Rosenthal J. Human internal auditory canal. *Arch Otolaryngol*1969;89:709-14.
- [6]. PapangelouL. Studyof the human internal auditory canal. *Laryngoscope*1972;82:617-24.
- [7]. Papangelou L. Volumetric study of the human internal auditory canal. *J LaryngolOtoI*1974;88:349-53
- [8]. House WF, Brackmann DE: Dizziness
- [9]. Amjad AH, Scheer AA, Rosenthal J: due to stenosis of the internal auditory canal, Human internal auditory canal. *Arch Otolarin Silverstein H, Norrell H (eds): Neurologi- yngol 89:709-714, 1969 cal Surgery of the Ear. Birmingham. Ala, Aesculapius Publishing Co, 1977, chap 16, pp*
- [10]. Gavilan AC, Suarez NC: Estenosis del conductoauditivointerno. *Acta Otorinolaryngol Iber Am* 23:830-839, 1972
- [11]. Rubinstein, D.; Sand berg, E. J. &Cajade-Law, A. G. Anatomy of the facial and vestibulocochlear nerves in the internal auditory canal. *AJNR Am. J. Neuroradiol.*, 17(6):1099-105, 1996.
- [12]. Drake, R.; Vogl, A.W. & Mitchell, A.W. *Gray's Anatomy for Students. E-Book 2009: Elsevier Health Sciences*
- [13]. M. V. Kirtane. The internal Auditory Canal *Indian Journal of Otolaryngology.*1977;29(4):155-157.
- [14]. M. Fatih Erkoç et.al. Normative size evaluation of internal auditory canal with magnetic resonance imaging: review of 3786 patients. *Folia Morphol.*71(4):217–220.
- [15]. Day, J. D.; Kellogg, J. X.; Fukushima, T. & Giannotta, S. L. Microsurgical anatomy of the inner surface of the petrous bone: neuroradiological and morphometric analysis as an adjunct to the retrosigmoid transmeatal approach. *Neurosurgery*, 34 (6):1003-8, 1994
- [16]. Bozbuga, M.; Öztürk, A.; Ari, Z.; Sahinoglu, K.; Bayraktar, B.; Polat, G. & Gürel, I. Surgical anatomy of the temporal bone and measurements of the skull base for transpetrosal approaches. *Okajimas Folia Anat. Jpn.*, 75(1):33-9, 1998.
- [17]. Akin Saygin D ; Nur Turkoglu F , Aydin Kabakci Turkoglu , F.; Aydin Kabakci , A. D. & ALPA, S. Poro acústicointerno: Diferenteshitosóseos y sus implicacionesclínicas. *Int. J. Morphol.*, 40(5):1368-1375, 2022
- [18]. Kolagi, S.; Heruru, A.; Ugale, M.; Manjula, R. &Mutalik, A. Suboccipital retrosigmoid surgical approach for internal auditory canal-a morphometric anatomical study on dry human temporal bones. *Indian J. Otolaryngol.*, 62 (4):372-5, 2010.
- [19]. Ebenius, B., 1934. Results of examination of petrous bone in auditory nerve tumors. *Acta Radiologica*, 15, 284-290.
- [20]. Sakashita, T. & Sando, I. Postnatal development of internal auditor canal studied by computer aided three dimensional reconstruction and measurements. *Ann. Otol. Rhinol. Laryngol.*, 104(6):469-75, 1995
- [21]. Valvassori, G. E. & Piece, R. H., 1964. The normal internal auditory canal. *American Journal of Roentgenology*, 92, 1233-1241.
- [22]. Mamatha Y, Trisha. K. R, Vishal Kumar. Anthropometry of Internal acoustic meatus in Dry adult human skull using casting method *Int J Anat Res* 2019;7(1.1):6113-6118. DOI: 10.16965/ijar.2018.417.